

Workforce Agility and Classroom Disposition of Teachers

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Sarangani District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2024-2025. Research instruments on workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the study found to exhibit a very high level of workforce agility, there is a very high level of classroom disposition of teachers, there is a significant relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers. This implies that the higher the workforce agility, the higher is the classroom disposition of teachers. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers was rejected.

Keywords: workforce agility, classroom disposition of teachers, school administration and supervision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dispositions of teachers play a key role in determining how teachers mobilize their intellectual resources and professional commitments in impacting student learning. It affects how teachers behave as moral educators of children, as role models, and as persons in authority. Teachers' dispositions in the classroom directly affect their effectiveness as educators. Without good dispositions, teachers are unmotivated, indifferent, and show unconcern to students and lack the inner drive to help improve students' progress in school (Buffone, 2021).

Conversely, a teacher may hold professional knowledge and or skills but simply not possess the disposition to act. This may manifest itself in behavior such as not grading papers in a timely manner, using unfair grading procedures, disregarding students' special needs, assigning inappropriate homework, failing to consider or allow various viewpoints in the classroom, and acting unethically, dishonestly, or illegally as professed by Morien (2018).

Meanwhile, the knowing how to control oneself is one important skill that needs to be developed. In the absence of this ability, one would find it hard to achieve something no matter how good he might feel about oneself. Cognitive emotional regulation means being able to monitor and control one's behavior, emotion, or thoughts, and improve them accordance according to what is socially acceptable. Teachers need a sense of emotional regulation to perform well in work (Mundiri, Mahmud, Ubaidillah, Azizah, Zuhro & Hasanah, 2021).

In the life of a teacher, every day is a constant challenge overcoming the many problems that test the toughness of their spirit. Teachers should be able to manage their emotions and check how they should appropriately respond to every situation or they will experience trouble. There is a necessity among teachers to regularly check their emotions (Menon & Suresh, 2022).

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In addition, these authors also indicated that teachers suffer emotional dysregulation in class while dealing with students of different social background. They said that teachers sometimes respond inappropriately. They become impatient and overly reactive that they tend to forget that stress brings adverse effects to their health. Thus, teachers are oftentimes encouraged to take things lightly especially problems on students' misbehavior (Galés & Gallon, 2019).

With the literature that underscores the relationship between cognitive emotional regulation and classroom disposition, the researcher would like to know if this relationship could be enhanced or affected if another variable comes into the process. Different readings on this concern showed that one possible variable that may have bearing on either of the two variables discussed is school climate. Promoting a positive school climate will improve many different areas of teachers' behavior and practices. Teachers working in a positive climate will be more creative and perform better. By promoting a positive school culture, teachers develop a sense of community which makes them happier in their work. Positive school climate helps in establishing effective schools as it impacts teacher productivity, performance, collaboration, communication, satisfaction, and it can also energize and elicit support from parents and community (Alviani, Hilmiana, Widiyanto & Muizu, 2024).

However, schools are not always about good things as there are many problems confronting our schools such as bullying, harassment, and inadequate academic performance. Specifically, many teachers find the demands of being a professional educator in today's schools difficult and at times stressful. When work stress results in teacher burnout, it can have serious consequences for the health and happiness of teachers (McGarr, Passy, Murray & Liu, 2022).

It is in this context that the researcher would like to know the relationship between the variables under the study. The researcher has not come across of a similar study especially in the local context. This undertaking therefore can be considered as a new knowledge and an additional document to the existing information for each variable involved in the study. It is in this extensive perspective that the researcher decided to conduct the study.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers. Specifically, this study sought the answer to the following questions:

1. What is the level of workforce agility in terms of:
 - 1.1. change agility;
 - 1.2. mental agility;
 - 1.3. people agility, and
 - 1.4 results agility?
2. What is the level of classroom disposition of teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. perception about self;
 - 2.2. perception about other people;
 - 2.3. perception about subject field, and
 - 2.4 general frame of reference perception?
3. Is there a significant relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses will be treated at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers.

Pearson r. This was used to determine the significance of the relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Workforce Agility

Shown in Table 1 is the level of workforce agility with an overall mean of 3.68 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, people agility has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 3.67 or very high, mental agility, 3.64 or very high, results agility, 3.63 or very high, and change agility, 3.62 or very high. The result of the study is in consonance with the views of Johari, Abdul Wahat & Zaremohzzabieh (2021) who stated that agility in the workplace refers to an individual's ability to receive and transmit information about changes in their environment, as well as respond to such information in a timely and effective manner. Strategically, workplace agility refers to the ability to sustain a competitive advantage through the combination of speed and data-driven innovation. Workplace agility can also lead to enhanced productivity, higher employee engagement, and greater flexibility in response to external demand.

Table 1. Level of Workforce Agility

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Change Agility	3.62	Very High
Mental Agility	3.64	Very High
People Agility	3.67	Very High
Results Agility	3.63	Very High
Overall	3.68	Very High

This is also supported by Chen, Landa, Padilla & Yur-Austin (2021) who posited that an agile teacher has a mindset that allows them to constantly improve their understanding, grow, and apply new approaches they have acquired along the way to successfully navigate future challenges. If school as an organization wants to thrive, its school heads must be learning agile, which is a reliable measure of a person's leadership ability. Most principal will fail in their jobs because they lack this particular skill.

Likewise, Das, Mukhopadhyay & Suar (2023) and Pereira, Mellahi, Temouri, Patnaik & Roohanifar (2019) underscored that teacher agility is a defining characteristic of effective educators in the 21st century. It empowers teachers to respond to the diverse and changing needs of their students, navigate unexpected challenges, and continuously grow in their practice. As education continues to evolve, fostering and supporting teacher agility will be essential to building resilient, innovative, and inclusive learning environments. Teachers who are agile are not just surviving change—they are leading it.

Level of Classroom Disposition of Teachers

Shown in Table 2 is the level of classroom disposition of teacher with an overall mean of 3.68 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study. Among the enumerated indicators, perceptions about the purpose of education and process of learning ranked highest with a mean score of 3.78 or very high, perceptions about subject field, 3.68 or very high, perceptions about other people, 3.64 or very high, and perceptions about self, with a mean score or 3.62 or very high.

The result of the study is consistent with the views of Lim, Halim & Ramayah (2022) who maintains that classroom disposition of teachers has been identified as one factor for teacher quality. Effective teaching involves more than effective planning, instructional knowledge, and teaching skills. It also extends to professional dispositions. Classroom dispositions are actually similar to professional beliefs or values systems. It is also synonymous to professional modes of conduct and the ways in which beliefs and attitudes are displayed by teachers' actions in and out of the classroom.

Similarly, dispositions related to effective teaching have been defined in a number of ways over the years. To some educators, dispositions are the values, commitments, and professional ethics that influence behaviors toward students, families, colleagues, and communities that affect student learning, motivation, and development as well as the educator's own professional growth. Dispositions are steered by attitudes and beliefs related to values like caring, honesty, fairness, empathy respectfulness, responsibility, and thoughtfulness (Muduli & Choudhury, 2024).

Table II. Level of Classroom Disposition of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Perceptions about Self	3.62	Very High
Perceptions about Other People	3.64	Very High
Perceptions about Subject Field	3.68	Very High
Perceptions about the Purpose of Education and Process of Learning	3.78	Very High
Overall	3.68	Very High

Significance on the Relationship between Workforce Agility and Classroom Disposition of Teachers

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.201 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers is rejected.

The result of the study is in congruence with the statement of Mesfin, Ghinea, Grønli & Hwang (2018) who believed that the relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition is vital to the success of modern education. Teachers who are agile in their professional roles are better equipped to foster engaging, responsive, and inclusive classrooms. Likewise, those with strong classroom dispositions are more prepared to develop and exercise agility in a changing educational landscape. By investing in both areas, educational institutions can create resilient, high-performing teaching communities that meet the needs of 21st-century learners.

This is also supported by Ghadampour & Zandkarimi (2019) who stated that in today's fast-changing educational environment, teachers are increasingly expected to respond swiftly to evolving demands, embrace innovation, and support diverse student needs. Two important concepts that help meet these expectations are workforce agility and classroom disposition. While they are often discussed separately, there is a deep and meaningful relationship between workforce agility and the classroom disposition of teachers. Together, they shape the teacher's capacity to adapt, connect, and lead effective classroom learning.

Table III. Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Communication Behavior and Student Engagement

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Workforce Agility and Classroom Disposition of Teachers	0.201	0.000	Reject

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a very high level of workforce agility. This means that the provisions relating to workforce agility is always manifested.

The study revealed a very high level of classroom disposition of teacher. This indicates that the provisions relating to classroom disposition of teacher are embodied in the item is always manifested.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers. This implies that the higher the level of workforce agility, the higher is the classroom disposition of teachers. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between workforce agility and classroom disposition of teachers was rejected.

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